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Abstract: A variety different solar thermal conversion systems can be used for driving a MED unit, namely: parabolic trough collectors, compound parabolic concentrators, evacuated tube collectors, flat plate collectors and salinity-gradient solar ponds. This paper deals with an experimental test campaign of a Multi-Effect Distillation (MED) unit installed at the Plataforma Solar Almería (PSA- CIEMAT) operated out of its nominal working conditions in order to provide experimental information required for design criteria and for the analysis of control strategies in solar MED plants. The MED plant (SOL-14) assessed is a conventional forward-feed unit with preheaters, 14 effects and nominal capacity of 3 m³/d. The experimental test campaign of the SOL14 plant conducted at the PSA proves that the PR exhibits low deviations within the range of working conditions analysed. The SOL-14 unit makes an efficient use of the energy consumption even when it is operated out of the nominal working conditions. The effects of part load operation are higher on distillate production than in PR. On the contrary, at working conditions over nominal, the PR suffers from higher deviation than distillate production, which remains unchanged within the range analysed.

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COVER LETTER

INTRODUCTION

First author, Mrs. P. Fernández Izquierdo, is Dpto. Ingeniería Energética, Universidad de Sevilla and PhD Mrs. L. García-Rodríguez from University of Seville (Spain) and I. Martín Mateos from University of La Laguna (Spain) are the current Supervisors of the P. Fernández Izquierdo PhD Thesis.

This paper is part of the P. Fernández Izquierdo PhD Thesis.

Multi-effect distillation is the most suitable desalination process to be driven by solar thermal collectors for medium to high-capacity range.

The Plataforma Solar de Almería (PSA), the main European solar thermal research centre, located in Southern Spain, has significantly contributed to the development of such a technology.

An absorption heat pump cycle in a multi-effect distillation (MED) process has been developed and tested in two different research and demonstration projects carried out at the Plataforma Solar de Almería.

In all previous studies that have been carried out, the MED process applied has never been considered to work out of its nominal conditions.

In this paper the results of the experimental assessment of Multi-effect distillation are reported. The MED plant is carrying out at partial load operation and out of nominal working conditions in order to provide information required for design criteria and for analysis of control strategies in solar MED plants.

Interesting and surprising results have been obtained and reported for the community.

EXPERTISE OF Dr L. GARCÍA RODRÍGUEZ

Dr Lourdes García Rodríguez has been leading the desalination research team of the University of La Laguna until September, 2007, when she moved to the University of Seville. This team has been financially supported by European, national and local authorities and private companies. She supervised 4 doctoral theses, and has another three predoctoral student to date. She is author or co-author of 36 papers in international journals (published or in-press). She is author of a book chapter edited by Springer, and co-author of a book edited by CIEMAT, another edited by UPV and several contributions to International Conferences. She also has educational experience on desalination powered by conventional energy (degree subjects: "Desalination plants" and "Desalination" (Bsc. Engineering) and renewable energy-powered desalination in two postgraduate courses ("Master en energías Renovables", Universidad de La Laguna y "Master en Sistemas de Energía Térmica", Universidad de Sevilla). Her research activities in renewable energy-powered desalination started in 1992. In a first stage, thermodynamic simulations and thermo-economic assessments of solar distillation and wind-powered reverse osmosis were performed in order to identify the most interesting improvements in renewable energy-powered desalination processes. In a second stage, since 2001, these improvements are being analysed: solar thermal-driven reverse osmosis; the use of absorption heat pumps in solar distillation, and solar membrane distillation. She has reviewed papers for several journals with impact index: Desalination, Solar Energy, Applied Energy and J. of Membrane Science.

INTERNATIONAL PUBLICATIONS

Chapter of books:

1. García-Rodríguez, L. Assessment of most promising development in solar desalination. *En: Solar Desalination for the 21st Century*. Eds: Luzzio Rizzuti y Hisham Ettouney, 2007. Springer, ISBN: 978-1-4020-5506-5. pp. 355- 369.

Invited papers:

2. García-Rodríguez, L. *Renewable energy applications in desalination. State of the Art.* *Solar Energy*, 75, 2003, pp. 381- 393.
3. García Rodríguez, L.; *Desalination by Wind Power.* *Wind Engineering*, 28, 2004, pp. 453-466.

Papers:

a) *General desalination reviews/assessments*

4. García Rodríguez, L.; *Exergoenvironmental analysis of seawater desalination.* *Desalination* (Accepted).
5. García-Rodríguez, L. *Seawater Desalination Driven by Renewable Energies, a review.* *Desalination*, 143(2), 2002, pp.103- 113.
6. García-Rodríguez, L.; Palmero-Marrero, A. I., y Gómez-Camacho, C. *Comparison of Solar Thermal Technologies for Applications to Seawater Desalination.* *Desalination*, 142(2), 2002, pp.135-142.
7. García-Rodríguez, L.; y Gómez-Camacho, C. *Perspectives of Solar-assisted Desalination.* *Desalination*, 136(1-3), 2001, pp. 213- 218.

b) *Solar membrane distillation*

8. Vega-Beltrán, J. C.; García-Rodríguez, L.; Martín-Mateos, I., y Blanco Gálvez, J. *Solar membrane distillation: theoretical assessment of multi-stage concept.* *Desalination and Water Treatment*, 18, 2010, pp. 133-138. doi: 10.5004/dwt.2010.1363.
9. Blanco Gálvez, J.; García-Rodríguez, L., and Martín-Mateos, I. *Stand-Alone Seawater Desalination by Innovative Solar-Powered Membrane-Thermal Distillation System: MEDESOL project.* *Desalination*, 246, 2009, pp. 567-576.

c) *Multieffect distillation coupled to absorption heat pumps*

10. Alarcón-Padilla, Diego-César; García-Rodríguez, Lourdes; Blanco-Gálvez, Julián; *Design recomendations for a multi-effect distillation plant connected to a double-effect absorbtion heat pump: a solar desalination case-study.* *Desalination*, 262 (1-3), 2010, pp.11-14.
11. Alarcón-Padilla, Diego-César; García-Rodríguez, Lourdes; Blanco-Gálvez, Julián; *Connection of absorption heat pumps to multi-effect distillation systems: pilot test facility at the Plataforma Solar de Almería (Spain).* *Desalination and Water Treatment*, 2010, pp.126-132. doi: 10.5004/dwt.2010.1362
12. Alarcón-Padilla, Diego-César; García-Rodríguez, Lourdes; Blanco-Gálvez, Julián; *Experimental assessment of connection of an absorbtion heat pump to a multi-effect distillation unit.* *Desalination*, 250, 2010, pp. 500-505.
13. Alarcón-Padilla, D.-C.; Blanco-Gálvez, J.; García-Rodríguez, L.; Gernjak, W., y Malato-Rodríguez, S. *First experimental results of a new hybrid solar/gas multi-effect distillation system: the AQUASOL Project.* *Desalination*, 220(1), 2008, pp. 619-625.

14. Alarcón-Padilla, D. C. y García-Rodríguez, L.: *Application of absorption heat pumps to multi-effect distillation: a case study of solar desalination* Desalination, 212, 2007, pp. 294-302.
15. Alarcón-Padilla, D. C.; García-Rodríguez, L., y Blanco-Gálvez, J.: *Assessment of an absorption heat pump coupled to a multi-effect distillation unit within AQUASOL project.* Desalination, 212, 2007, pp. 303-310.

d) *Solar thermal-driven reverse osmosis*

16. Delgado-Torres, A., and García-Rodríguez, L., *Preliminary design of seawater and brackish water desalination system driven by low-temperature solar organic rankine cycles.* Energy Conversion and Management, 51(12), 2010, pp.2913-1920.
17. Delgado-Torres, A. M., and García-Rodríguez, L. *Analysis and optimization of the low-temperature solar organic Rankine cycle (ORC).* Energy Conversion and Management, 51(12), 2010, pp. 2846-2856.
18. García-Rodríguez, L., and Delgado-Torres, A., *Solar-powered Rankine cycles for fresh water production.* Desalination, 212, 2007, pp. 319- 327.
19. Delgado-Torres, A., and García-Rodríguez, L., *Status of Solar thermal-driven reverse osmosis desalination.* Desalination, 216, 2007, pp. 242-251.
20. Delgado-Torres, A., and García-Rodríguez, L., *Preliminary assessment of solar organic Rankine cycles for driving a desalination system.* Desalination, 216, 2007, pp. 252-275.
21. Delgado-Torres, A., and García-Rodríguez, L., *Comparison of solar technologies for driving a desalination system by means of an organic Rankine cycle.* Desalination,216, 2007, pp. 276-291.
22. Delgado-Torres, A.; García-Rodríguez, L., and Romero Ternero, V. *Preliminary design of a solar thermal-powered seawater reverse osmosis system.* Desalination, 216, 2007, pp. 292-305.
23. Delgado-Torres, A., and García-Rodríguez, L., *Double cascade organic Rankine cycles for solar-driven reverse osmosis desalination.* Desalination, 216, 2007, pp. 306-313.
24. García-Rodríguez, L., and Blanco-Gálvez, J.: *Solar-heated Rankine cycles for water and electricity production: POWERSOL project.* Desalination, 212, 2007, pp. 311-318.

e) *Wind-powered reverse osmosis*

25. García-Rodríguez, L.; Romero-Ternero, V., and Gómez Camacho, C., *Economic Analysis of Wind Powered Desalination.* Desalination, 137, 2001, pp. 259- 265.
26. Romero-Ternero, V.; García-Rodríguez, L., and Gómez Camacho, C., *Thermoeconomic analysis of wind powered seawater reverse osmosis desalination in the Canary Islands.* Desalination, 186, 2005, pp. 291-298.

f) *Reverse osmosis*

27. Romero-Ternero, V.; García-Rodríguez, L.; and Gómez-Camacho, C., *Thermoeconomic Analysis of a Seawater Reverse Osmosis Plant.* Desalination, 181, 2005, p. 43-59.
28. Romero-Ternero, V.; García-Rodríguez, L.; and Gómez-Camacho, C., *Exergy Analysis of a Seawater Reverse Osmosis Plant.* Desalination, 175, 2005, 197-207.
29. Peñate, B. and García-Rodríguez, L. Energy optimisation of existing SWRO (Seawater Reverse Osmosis Plants) with ERT (Energy Recovery Turbines): technical and thermoeconomic assessment. Energy Journal, 36, 2011, pp. 613-626.

30. Peñate, B. and García-Rodríguez, L. Retrofitting assessment of Lanzarote IV seawater reverse osmosis desalination plant. *Desalination*, 266(1-3), 2011, pp. 244-255.

g) Desalination processes integrated in solar power plants

31. A.S. Nafey, M.A. Sharaf and L. García-Rodríguez, A new visual library for design and simulation of solar desalination systems (SDS). *Desalination* 259 (2010) 197–207.
32. A.S. Nafey, M.A. Sharaf and L. García-Rodríguez, Thermo-economic analysis of a combined solar organic Rankine cycle-reverse osmosis desalination process with different energy recovery configurations. *Desalination* 261 (2010) 138–147.
33. M. A. Sharaf, A. S. Nafey and L. García-Rodríguez. Exergy and Thermo-economic Analysis of a Combined Solar Organic Cycle with Multi Effect Distillation (MED) Desalination Process. *Desalination*, 272 (2011) 135-147.
34. M. A. Sharaf, A. S. Nafey and L. García-Rodríguez. Thermo-economic Analysis of Solar Thermal Power Cycles Assisted Multi Effect Distillation-Vapor Compression (MED-VC) Desalination Processes. *Energy Journal*. Accepted.

h) Solar distillation (Multieffect and multi-stage flash distillation)

35. García-Rodríguez, L.; Palmero-Marrero, A. I. and Gómez-Camacho, C., *Thermoeconomic Optimisation of the Sol-14 plant (Plataforma Solar de Almería, Spain)*. *Desalination*, 136 (1-3), 2001, pp. 219- 223.
36. García-Rodríguez, L.; and Gómez-Camacho, C., *Exergy Analysis of the SOL-14 plant (Plataforma Solar de Almería, Spain)*. *Desalination*, 137(1-3), 2001, pp. 251-258.
37. García-Rodríguez, L., and Gómez-Camacho, C., Thermoeconomic Analysis of a Solar Multieffect Distillation Plant Installed at the Plataforma Solar de Almería (Spain). *Desalination*, 122, 1999, pp. 205-214.
38. García Rodríguez, L.; Palmero-Marrero, A. I.; and Gómez Camacho, C., *Application of Direct Steam Generation into a Solar Parabolic Trough Collector to Multieffect Distillation*. *Desalination*, 125(1-3), 1999, pp. 139- 145.
39. García-Rodríguez, L., and Gómez-Camacho, C., *Preliminary Design and Cost analysis of a Solar Distillation System*. *Desalination*, 126(1-3), 1999, pp. 109-114.
40. García-Rodríguez, L., and Gómez-Camacho, C., Conditions for Economical Benefits of the use of Solar Energy in Multistage Flash Distillation. *Desalination*, 125(1-3), 1999, pp. 133-138.
41. García-Rodríguez, L.; and Gómez-Camacho, C., *Thermoeconomic Analysis of a Solar Parabolic Trough Distillation Plant*. *Desalination*, 122, 1999, pp. 215-224.
42. García-Rodríguez, L.; and Gómez-Camacho, C., Design Parameters Selection of a Distillation System Coupled to a Solar Parabolic Trough Collector Field. *Desalination*, 122, 1999, pp. 195-204.

i) Other topics

43. Giacovazzo, C.; Siliqi, D., y García-Rodríguez, L.; *On integrating Direct Methods and Isomorphous Replacement Techniques: triplets estimation and treatment of errors*. *Acta Cryst. Section A*, 57, 2001, pp. 571- 575.
44. García-Rodríguez, L.; González-Silgo, C.; Ruíz-Pérez, C.; and González-Platas, J. *APREFIS 1.0: a computer program for learning physics*. *Eur. J. Phys.*, 22, 2001, pp. 1-6.

RESEARCH HIGHLIGHTS

>The PSA-CIEMAT MED plant has been operated out of its nominal working conditions.>The effects of part load operation are higher on distillate production than in PR.> At working conditions over nominal, the PR suffers higher deviation >The results allow to expand the operating system range.>The knowledge about control has been improved.

Experimental analysis of a multi-effect distillation unit operated out of nominal conditions

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Abstract

A variety different solar thermal conversion systems can be used for driving a MED unit, namely: parabolic trough collectors, compound parabolic concentrators, evacuated tube collectors, flat plate collectors and salinity-gradient solar ponds. This paper deals with an experimental test campaign of a Multi-Effect Distillation (MED) unit installed at the Plataforma Solar Almería (PSA- CIEMAT) operated out of its nominal working conditions in order to provide experimental information required for design criteria and for the analysis of control strategies in solar MED plants. The MED plant (SOL-14) assessed is a conventional forward-feed unit with preheaters, 14 effects and nominal capacity of 3 m³/d. The experimental test campaign of the SOL14 plant conducted at the PSA proves that the PR exhibits low deviations within the range of working conditions analysed. The SOL-14 unit makes an efficient use of the energy consumption even when it is operated out of the nominal working conditions. The effects of part load operation are higher on distillate production than in PR. On the contrary, at working conditions over nominal, the PR suffers from higher deviation than distillate production, which remains unchanged within the range analysed.

Keywords: *seawater desalination; multi-effect distillation; solar distillation; experimental assessment*

1. Introduction

Multi-effect distillation is the most suitable desalination process to be driven by solar thermal collectors for medium to high-capacity range. The Plataforma Solar de Almería (PSA), the main European solar thermal research centre located in Southern Spain, has significantly contributed to the development of such a technology. Its most important contribution is the reliability demonstration of obtaining an overall Performance Ratio (PR) of 20 by coupling a Double-Effect Absorption Heat Pump (DEAHP) and a multi-effect distillation unit [1-5] within the framework of the European project AQUASOL (March 2002 – February 2006). The feasibility of this technology had been previously demonstrated at the PSA [6] with a first prototype of a DEAHP.

A variety different solar thermal conversion systems can be used for driving a MED unit, namely: parabolic trough collectors, compound parabolic concentrators, evacuated tube collectors, flat plate collectors and salinity-gradient solar ponds. Literature reviews show intensive research and demonstration activities in this field [7-9]. Even though the selected solar

1 thermal energy system includes thermal storage, an important issue in the control system of a
2 solar MED plant is the decision of shutting down the MED unit when the thermal storage are
3 not able to provide a given level of thermal power at a given value of temperature. This decision
4 strongly depends on the behaviour of the MED unit operated at part load, although the selection
5 of aforementioned values of temperature and power input available may depend on:

- 6 - the specific solar collector and thermal storage
- 7 - the climatic conditions
- 8 - availability of conventional energy backup.

9 Besides that, other design issues also depend on the performance at part load operation as:

- 10 - sizing the solar field over its design point, or
- 11 - selecting the thermal storage capacity.

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14 Moreover, the sizing of the thermal storage and solar field also depend on the decision about
15 operating the MED unit above its nominal capacity in order to consume the surplus energy
16 provided by the solar field around noon in summer periods. The analysis of this issue requires
17 the experimental assessment of the MED unit when it consumes thermal power above nominal
18 temperature and/or nominal power.

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21 This paper deals with the experimental test campaign of a multi-effect distillation unit installed
22 at the PSA operated out of its nominal working conditions in order to provide experimental
23 information required for design criteria and for the analysis of control strategies in solar MED
24 plants.

25 26 27 2. Experimental system and test campaign

28
29 The Multi-Effect Distillation plant (MED) called SOL-14, located in the Plataforma Solar de
30 Almería, is a conventional forward feed unit with preheaters consisting of 14 effects vertically
31 stacked. After being preheated at the end condenser and preheaters, seawater is sprayed on the
32 external surface of the horizontal tube bundle of the first cell evaporator, which receives
33 external thermal power. The remaining brine goes on to the second effect, where it is sprayed on
34 the evaporator. A small part of the steam generated in the first effect preheats the seawater while
35 the main part reaches the evaporator of the next stage providing the required thermal power to
36 continue the partial evaporation of the feed water. Similar condensation/evaporation processes
37 are repeated from the second to the 14th effect. The steam generated in the last effect is
38 condensed in the final condenser (cooled by seawater).

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41 SOL-14 plant was manufactured by ENTROPIE in 1987 [10]. Within the framework of
42 AQUASOL project [11], the first cell of the original plant was replaced in order to permit the
43 thermal power consumption by means of liquid water instead of steam. The plant is currently
44 connected to a stationary solar field consisting in compound parabolic concentrators
45 manufactured by Ao Sol [12]. Water is used as heat transfer fluid of the solar field, which is
46 heated as it circulates through the solar collectors and is then stored in the hot tank. Hot water
47 from the storage system provides the MED plant with the required thermal power consumption.

Figure 1. SOL-14 plant. Plataforma Solar de Almería (PSA), CIEMAT, Spain.

SOL-14 DESALINATION PLANT (NOMINAL)	
Sea-Water flow	8 m ³ /h
Brine reject	5 m ³ /h
Distillate production	3 m ³ /h
Seawater flow at condenser:	
at 10°C	8 m ³ /h
at 25°C	20 m ³ /h
Output salinity	5 ppm TDS
Number of cells	14
Heat source energy consumption	190 kW
Performance Ratio	>9
Vacuum system	Hydroejectors (seawater at 3 bar)
Top brine temperature	70°C
Condenser temperature	35°C

Table 1. Technical specifications of the Sol-14 MED unit.

In order to assess the behaviour of the SOL-14 plant at partial load operation, the following experimental procedure was carried out:

- Variable temperature and thermal power of the external energy consumption: the range of temperature selected is from 57°C to 74°C.
- Seawater flow rate through the end condenser: variable to maintain a temperature difference of 35°C between the 1st and 14th effects ($\Delta T = T_1 - T_{14} = 35^\circ\text{C}$). This operation conditions results in temperature gradient across the heat transfer surfaces similar to nominal working conditions.

Table 2 summarises main parameters of different working conditions in the test campaign conducted.

TEST	TEMPERATURE OF THE THERMAL INPUT (°C)	THERMAL POWER INPUT (kW)
1	57	137
2	60	153
3	63	166
4	65	191
5	68	182
6	70	195
7	72	203
8	74	207

Table 2. Average values of temperature and thermal power input in the test campaign.

3. Experimental results

Figure 2 shows a preliminary test in which the MED unit is operated at constant temperature of the thermal input and nominal power input. The test is performed at the recommended value for summer conditions, 74°C, which results in a distillate production approximately constant around the nominal production 3 m³/h and a PR around 10.

Figure 2. Distillate Production when MED plant is operating in nominal conditions.

Performance ratio and distillate production are the main parameters to assess the suitability of:

- operating the MED unit below nominal working conditions instead of shutting down within periods with low availability of thermal power and /or temperature in the energy subsystem – i.e. solar field and thermal storage -.
- operating the MED unit above nominal working conditions instead of wasting the surplus energy or oversizing the thermal storage.

A representative set of results is depicted in Figures 3 and 4. They show eight different working conditions given in Table 2. Table 3 summarises experimental test results by providing average values of every test.

Finally, Table 4 show deviations from nominal working conditions of the quantities showed in Table 3 in order to analyse general results of the test campaign.

Figure 3. Distillate production at eight different temperatures of the thermal input. The corresponding power inputs are depicted in figure 4

Figure 4. Performance ratio and thermal power consumption at eight different working conditions (See Table 2).

TEST	TEMPERATURE OF THE THERMAL INPUT (°C)	THERMAL POWER CONSUMPTION (kW)	DISTILLATE PRODUCTION (m ³ /h)	PR
1	57°C	137	1.9	8.9
2	60°C	153	2.2	9.1
3	63°C	166	2.4	9.3
4	65°C	191	2.7	9.0
5	68°C	182	2.9	10
6	70°C	195	2.9	9.5
7	72°C	203	3.0	9.4
8	74°C	207	3.0	9.3

Table 3. Average values of the experimental results from Figures 3-4.

TEST	TEMPERATURE DEVIATION, (%)	THERMAL POWER DEVIATION, (%)	PRODUCTION DEVIATION, (%)	PERFORMANCE RATIO DEVIATION, (%)
1	-19	-28	-37	-11
2	-14	-19	-27	-9
3	-10	-13	-20	-7
4	-7	1	-10	-10
5	-3	-4	-3	0
6	0	3	-3	-5
7	3	7	0	-6
8	6	9	0	-7

Table 4. Deviation from nominal conditions of results given in Table 3.

3. Conclusions

To sum up, the experimental test campaign of the SOL14 plant conducted at the PSA proves that the PR exhibits low deviations within the range of working conditions analysed. Therefore, as a general conclusion, the SOL-14 unit makes an efficient use of the energy consumption even when it is operated out of the nominal working conditions. The effects of part load operation are higher on distillate production than in PR. On the contrary, at working conditions over nominal, the PR suffers from higher deviation than distillate production, which remains unchanged within the range analysed.

Some quantitative results from tests 1 to 5 (part load operation) and from tests 6 to 8 (working conditions over nominal) are summarised below:

- PR exhibits a maximum deviation of 11% in the worse working conditions analysed, corresponding to thermal power input of 28% below nominal (190kW) and temperature of 57°C (19% below nominal temperature, 70°C).
- The corresponding maximum deviation of the distillate production obtained is 37% in the worse working conditions analysed.
- Simultaneous deviations of temperature and power in the heat input below 10 % above nominal working conditions result in PR deviations below 8% while distillate production is not affected.

Finally, although final design and control recommendation for solar MED plants should be based on a thorough analysis of specific climatic conditions and selected solar field and thermal storage, the following preliminary recommendations may be concluded:

- The MED unit should be operated even if the available thermal power and temperature are quite below nominal values. This recommendation should result in increasing the solar fraction with an efficient use of the solar resources.
- The sizing of the solar field and thermal storage should avoid operation of the MED unit over nominal working conditions since the PR decrease without increasing the distillate production.

4. References

1. D. C. Alarcón-Padilla, L. García-Rodríguez, J. Blanco-Gálvez, *Design recommendations for a multi-effect distillation plant connected to a double-effect absorption heat pump: a solar desalination case-study*. Desalination, 262 (1-3), 2010, pp.11-14.
2. D. C. Alarcón-Padilla, L. García-Rodríguez, J. Blanco-Gálvez, *Connection of absorption heat pumps to multi-effect distillation systems: pilot test facility at the Plataforma Solar de Almería (Spain)*. Desalination and Water Treatment, 2010, pp.126-132. doi: 10.5004/dwt.2010.1362
3. D. C. Alarcón-Padilla, L. García-Rodríguez, J. Blanco-Gálvez, Julián; *Experimental assessment of connection of an absorption heat pump to a multi-effect distillation unit*. Desalination, 250, 2010, pp. 500-505.
4. D. C. Alarcón-Padilla, y L. García-Rodríguez, *Application of absorption heat pumps to multi-effect distillation: a case study of solar desalination* Desalination, 212, 2007, pp. 294-302.
5. D. C. Alarcón-Padilla, L. García-Rodríguez, y J. Blanco-Gálvez, *Assessment of an absorption heat pump coupled to a multi-effect distillation unit within AQUASOL project*. Desalination, 212, 2007, pp. 303-310.
6. E. Zarza, 1994. Solar Thermal Desalination Project. Phase II Results & Final Project Report, 1st ed. CIEMAT, Madrid, Spain.
7. J. Blanco, S. Malato, P. Fernández, D. Alarcón, W. Gernjak, and M. I. Maldonado, Review of feasible solar energy applications to water processes. Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews, 13, 2009, pp. 1437-1445.
8. L. García-Rodríguez, Assessment of most promising development in solar desalination. *En: Solar Desalination for the 21st Century*. Eds: Luzzio Rizzuti y Hisham Ettouney, 2007. Springer, ISBN: 978-1-4020-5506-5. pp. 355- 369.
9. L. García-Rodríguez, *Renewable energy applications in desalination. State of the Art*. Solar Energy, 75, 2003, pp. 381- 393.
10. E. Zarza, 1991. Solar Thermal Desalination Project. First Phase Results and Second Phase Description, 1st ed. CIEMAT, Madrid, Spain.
11. <http://www.psa.es/webeng/aquasol/index.php> (24.03.2011)

Figure

Figure

TEST RESULTS OBTAINED ON MAY 6th, 2010

Figure

Figure

POWER CONSUMED BY PLANT (KW), PERFORMANCE RATIO.

